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IRX transcription factors function in transformation and metastasis.

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IRX family transcription factors operate in a transformation centric network. Primary method of discovery was whole transcriptome based transcriptional co-regulation analysis of IRX1, IRX2 and IRX3. Rationale was discovery research into IRX function promoted by observation of IRX modulation in lymph node metastasis in human cancer in a deadly brain cancer, DIPG (diffuse intrinsic pontine glioma). We present evidence indicating a steroidigenic- or hormone-based mechanism of action for IRX factors in transformation.